

PROBLEMS OF SPEECH IMPACT

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Abstract.

This article deals about expressive means of speech influence, their appropriate use, the impact of new aspects in TV broadcasting on speech culture, social factors of speech identities.

Key words.

television speech, colloquial influence, language norms, methodological updates, sound imagery, tautology, pleonasm.

The speech effect, as one of the main elements of the communication process, implies the perception of the information that the addressee wants to convey and the expression of a reaction to it. In this process, language acts as a means of coordinating the joint activities of people. Any speech activity, in contrast to a special form of influence, is dynamic in nature and is happening in a way that depends on various intralinguistic and extralinguistic factors. "Despite the growing importance of the internet, television media remains an important segment in the system. In recent decades, the principles of television, the genre-thematic content of the broadcast, the peculiarities of the use of expressive means have undergone serious changes. The impact of technological progress and the changes in the needs and requirements of the audience associated with it necessitate the search for new ways to present information. As a result, medietext forms are developing in the media, the language of presenting information is changing, new formats are being introduced in order to make it more convenient and interesting to receive information [1,135-138]."

Television speech, in the way of a manifestation of a universal language, is somewhat independent, it can be said that it has its own laws, which, although it seems that it is developing irreplaceable, have formed over the years. The range of problems of learning modern television speech is wide. Issues such as the structure of television speech, its own characteristics, methodological syntax, image and text

radios', the influence of televisions' speech on the national language, the level of penetration into everyday speech, the individual approach of the presenter/journalist, style, intonation mold are important areas that dictate the study of linguists.

Yu.A.Oganesova classifies the voice imagery of televisions' speech into verbal and nonverbal types. Verbal (colloquial) imagery includes both supersegment elements such as sound pace and timbre, intonation, and textual characters such as phraseological compounds, professionalisms, application of tropes, selection of syntactic constructions. And to nonverbal audio expressive means implies the use of musical harmony, interplay, sound design elements[2].

A.I.Anoxin, referring to the marked nature of television, divides expressive means into two types - conditional and figurative ones. As the main conditional character used by television, the scientist names the word, text, and notes that the functions of the text in TV journalism are sharply different from those in other media. The text component of the video content is a variant of the image displayed on the screen that is harmonized with the content. In the process of communication with the viewer, telenutq creates a direct dialogue effect, which in turn forms the effect of trust [3,276-280].

Despite the on-screen nature of television data, video sequences are not always enough to understand the essence of events, so the semantic load on television content, most often, falls on the text. Hence, the requirements for the text are brightness, expressiveness, clarity, ease of perception and brevity [4,135-138].

The "softening" of official censorship greatly reduced the distance between television and the viewer, and this social factor led to deviations in the television station system, in its general nature, and especially in its attitude to language. First of all, the determination to follow the norms of the literary language is weakened. For example, the control of the sound timbre, diction quality, correct pronunciation rules characteristic of phonostilistics has decreased. Lexically, the use of dialect-specific or parasitic words, varvarism, vulgarisms increased. Errors also began to be observed in syntactic line units (sentence and text-making technology). The tendency of sukhandon to speak freely, and not from the finished text, opened a wide path to colorful ways of reflecting reality.

G.L.Kovalchuk describes the changes taking place in television speech as follows: "First of all, not only the number of participants in Mass Communication has increased, but their qualitative characteristics - gender, age, social status-have also become more diverse within the boundaries of one communication movement.

Secondly, experts note that confidence is gaining momentum in open, calm speech, as spontaneous speech begins to prevail. Even if the text is written in advance, they try to speak, not read. The emptiness of speech leads to a decrease in the general culture of speech. This condition is manifested in violations of language standards:

- tautology
- pleonasm, lexical redundancy
- errors in the conjugation of words in a sentence
- orthoepic and methodological errors."[5,67-71]

Tautology (Greek. tautologia-exactly the same word) - 1) repeated overuse of one thought, content with another word or words (vocabulary, sentence), over-repetition of the word. For example, true truth, to speak, as completely and completely [6].

Assalomu alaykum. "Sehr-joduga uchradim" mavzusida ko'rsatuv olyapmiz, bundan xabariz bor. Siz ham hozir lavhada ko'rgan insonlarimiz qatorida sehr-joduga uchragan insonlardan birisiz. Nima bo'lgan? Qani, aytib bering-chi. (From the talk show" people among us").

Pleonasm (Greek. pleonasmos-redundancy) is the semantically repeated application of homogeneous or synonymous means of Expression (Language units [7].

O'zbekistonga xorijlik mehmonlar kelar ekan, manzillarni sayohat qilar ekan turli yo'nalishlar bo'yicha mamlakatni baholashadi va ular yuqoridagi kabi holatlarni ham albatta inobatga olishadi, shak - shubhasiz.

Confirmation, of course in the sense of emphasis, was caused by pleonasm as a result of the use of shaky modal words in a single sentence.

Cases of violation of grammatical norms in the interplay of words in a sentence are also frequent.

Mana shunday hozir lavhada ko'rgan holatlarni agar, o'zimizni yaqinlarimizda kuzatadigan bo'lsak, albatta, menimcha, bu issiq-sovuq yo'g'amas, bor degan fikram keladi odamga. (From the talk show" people among us").

There is an increasing number of shows in the form of talk shows, debates, open communication, in which it is possible to positively assess whether spectators actively participate and freely express their opinions, of course. But this does not mean that speaker or the TV presenter can also withdraw from the norms of the literary language and lead the show in a simple colloquial language emin-free, untidy. The above sentence, first of all, does not necessarily correspond to the norms of the literary language in terms of syntactic construction. Also, when

pronouncing certain units of language, the grammatical and orthoepic norms were not followed in the manner of our loved ones - our own loved ones, creamy ones - no, my opinion - no.

Based on our observations, we want to mention that in addition to these, there are also cases of "misapplication of words". For example, gross errors such as using ATI in 4 instead of just 4 combinations, in the manner of trying to do the best, are caused by a lack of deep philological knowledge, ignorance of the meaning and nature of the word. Making such errors in the broadcast text, which is presented to millions of viewers, has reduced the power of the speech effect.

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